

THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HOMOGENEOUS CAST MMCS

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ABSTRACT

The engulfment of TiC reinforcing particles into the primary Al grains of commercial purity, Al-4wt%Cu and Al-7wt%Si-0.3wt%Mg (A356) matrices has been encouraged by a novel fabrication route. The Young's moduli of composites produced by this route closely follow the rule of mixtures predictions for modulus variation with volume percent reinforcement added. The high modulus increases, for a reinforcement with a relatively low modulus compared to SiC and Al₂O₃, are attributed to very effective load transfer achieved through strong particle-matrix interfacial bonding. This increased bond strength is thought to have been brought about by encouraging primary Al nucleation and growth on the reinforcing particle surfaces.

INTRODUCTION

There are several techniques available for making metal matrix composites (MMCs) ranging from powder metallurgy (PM) methods to casting. One of the most economically attractive is the cast route which employs near standard foundry practise. Its other main advantages include the ability to fabricate to near-net shape and the potential for improved wetting of the reinforcement. There are, however, a number of disadvantages which limit the performance of the composite, these can be summarised as follows:

- some desirable particle-matrix combinations are impossible due to poor wetting of the particles by the liquid preventing their incorporation into the melt,
- reactions between the reinforcement and the liquid matrix may occur resulting in reinforcement dissolution or in brittle particle/matrix interfaces,
- high particle additions to the liquid result in low apparent composite fluidity which makes processing extremely difficult,
- segregation of particulate may occur as a result of sedimentation or particle pushing ahead of the growth fronts during solidification leading to undesirable, inhomogeneous, particle distributions,
- particle agglomeration may occur to form large brittle particle clusters.

In trying to minimise these problems it is often necessary to limit the type, size and volume fraction of the reinforcing phase and restrict the choice of alloy. This means that the maximum achievable mechanical properties are also limited. For these reasons, few cast composites have been considered for high strength-high modulus applications but instead are targeted for low cost applications requiring high wear resistance. Such composite design restrictions are not applicable to PM route material and this is reflected in their superior mechanical properties albeit at a significant cost penalty.

To date, the incorporation of particles into the melt and the control of particle segregation present the most significant obstacles to generating a wide range of high quality cast MMCs to rival powder-route material. These segregation problems stem from the nature of the fabrication process and from physical and chemical interactions between the particle and the matrix. Improvements in the mechanical properties might be expected if the homogeneity of the particle distribution could be improved, most conveniently through modifications to the fabrication process.

It is desirable to promote engulfment of the reinforcement within the advancing metal grains during solidification so that the particles are not associated with brittle inter-metallic phases and other particles in the inter-dendritic regions. The fact that engulfment occurs suggests that the solid metal has an affinity for the reinforcement and that the particle-matrix interfacial bonding will be good. If the modulus increase due to the introduction of a second phase is to be maximised, strong interfacial bonding is essential so that the externally applied load is transferred to the reinforcement. Strong interfacial bonding and homogeneous reinforcement distributions are also likely to delay the onset of particle-matrix de-cohesion thereby improving the composite's ductility.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Metal matrix composites were made by the addition of 10µm TiC particles to molten commercial purity (CP, 99.8% Al) aluminium by a proprietary process [1, 2]. This technique uses wetting agents to facilitate spontaneous transfer of the particles to the melt. Particle additions were made at different volume fractions and post alloying was performed to create in addition to CP Al matrix composites, Al-4wt%Cu and Al-7wt%Si-0.3wt%Mg (A356) alloy composites. The different materials produced are listed in table 1.

Cast composites were sectioned for metallographical analysis and inspected by optical microscopy for signs of agglomeration and inhomogeneous, inter-dendritic distributions of the reinforcing phase. As-cast reinforced and un-reinforced samples were machined into specimens for tensile testing and the modulus, ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the percent elongation to failure were measured. Al-4Cu specimens were tested in the T4 condition and A356 specimens were tested in the T6 condition. The mechanical behaviour of these composites was compared with those of re-melted *Duralcan* (A356-15 vol%, 20µm SiC) material cast in the same way and tested in the T6 condition.

Table 1. Combinations of reinforcement size, type, volume fraction and base alloy examined in the present study.

Matrix	Reinforcement vol. %	Reinforcement Type and Mean Particle Size
CP Al	5, 10, 15, 20	10 µm TiC
Al-4Cu	5, 10, 15	10 µm TiC
A356	15	10 µm TiC
A356	15 (<i>Duralcan</i>)	20 µm SiC

RESULTS

COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURES

CP Al. The distribution of the TiC particles in commercial purity Al is un-clustered and near homogeneous as can be seen in figure 1a. Extensive grain refinement was observed in the composite castings although not all the particles appeared to act as grain nuclei. Almost all the particles were engulfed within the aluminum grains. There was little observable difference in the homogeneity of the particle distribution with increasing particle volume fraction.

Al-4Cu Alloy. The spatial distribution of the reinforcement again appeared near homogeneous and the TiC particles were seldom severely clustered. Once again there was little observable effect of variations in the particle volume fraction on the homogeneity of the distribution. A noticeable effect of increased particle additions was more extensive grain refinement. The micrograph in figure 1b clearly shows that a significant proportion of the reinforcement is located intra-dendritically.

A356 Alloy. A larger number of the particles in this composite were associated with the interdendritic regions than in either of the other two composites (see figure 2a). It was interesting to note that grain refinement was less prominent in this system. Many particles are, however, located within the primary Al grains giving a much more homogenous distribution of the reinforcing phase than that which was observed in the re-melted SiC reinforced A356 *Duralcan* material (see figure 2b).

Figure 1. Optical micrographs showing the distribution of TiC particles in a) CP Al and b) Al-4wt%Cu.

Figure 2. Optical micrographs showing the distribution of a) TiC particles and b) SiC particles in A356.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

CP Al. The mechanical properties of TiC reinforced CP Al matrix composites are presented in figure 3a. The modulus and UTS, as expected, rise with increasing additions of reinforcement. Modulus improvements of roughly 50% (to 95 GPa) and UTS increases of 180% (to 150 MPa) were achieved with 20 vol% reinforcement additions. The elongation to failure in these specimens was uncharacteristically high, only dropping significantly below the un-reinforced value with additions of greater than 5 vol%. In figure 3b the modulus vs vol% TiC addition has been plotted along with rule of mixtures (ROM) predictions. These plots were constructed assuming the modulus of un-reinforced CP Al to be that which was measured experimentally (64 GPa) and values calculated with TiC modulus data of 230 and 400 GPa. These two values represent the extremes quoted in the literature [3]. It can be seen that the theoretical (ROM) plot is followed very closely for TiC modulus values of 230 GPa.

Al-4Cu. Figure 4a shows the modulus and percent elongation to failure data for the Al-4Cu system. Modulus improvements of the order of 30% (to 95 GPa) were obtained with the addition of 15 vol% reinforcement whilst maintaining reasonably high ductility (6%). The UTS measurements indicated an improvement from 253 MPa for un-reinforced material in the T4 condition, increasing to 300 MPa with the addition of 5 vol% of TiC particles. Specimens containing 10 and 15 vol% of particles were observed to contain large inclusions which led to their premature failure and a wide scatter in the results. Figure 4b shows the modulus vs vol% reinforcement plots for this system and there is again good agreement between experimental data and the rule of mixtures predictions for $E_{TiC} = 230$ GPa.

A356 Alloy. Table 2 shows mechanical property data for Al-7Si-0.3Mg (A356) reinforced and un-reinforced material in the T6 condition along with that for the re-melted, SiC-reinforced *Duralcan* material. The average modulus of the 15 vol% TiC-reinforced composite (96 GPa) is significantly higher than that of its SiC-reinforced counterpart (88 GPa), although the UTS and ductilities are slightly lower. The rule of mixtures plots for TiC and SiC-containing composites are presented in figure 5. From this it can be seen that the experimental data for TiC-based composites agrees more closely with ROM predictions than data for the SiC-reinforced composite does. Once more, the agreement is good when E_{TiC} is taken as 230 GPa. Whilst the UTS values for both reinforced materials are very low compared with those quoted in the literature [4], the modulus and ductility data are consistent with that reported for *Duralcan* material and other similar composites.

Figure 3. Mechanical property (a) and modulus vs vol% reinforcement (b) plots for TiC reinforcement in CP Al.

Figure 4. Mechanical property (a) and modulus vs vol% reinforcement (b) plots for TiC reinforcement in Al-4Cu.

Table 2. Mechanical property data for reinforced and un-reinforced A356 matrices in the T6 condition.

Composite	Modulus (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
A356 (T6)	72	260	5.7
A356 15v% TiC (T6)	96	134	1.0
A356 15v% SiC (T6)	88	174	1.3

Figure 5. Predicted modulus vs vol% reinforcement plots for TiC and SiC in A356 and experimental data.

Table 3 shows data for the mechanical properties of selected commercial composites (taken from reference [4]) along with results from this series of experiments (marked EXP). In this table, PM denotes that the material was made by a powder metallurgy route, C that the material was cast and E that it was extruded. Where appropriate, the manufacturer's name is in italics. All the reinforcement contents are in volume percent.

The best results for the modulus and ductility obtained in this study compare favourably those for commercial composites including material made by a powder route. The A356-15vol% TiC composite has a higher modulus than even its 20vol% SiC equivalent and moduli for the CP and Al-4Cu matrix materials compare well with those for the 6XXX and 2XXX series alloy composites respectively. Whilst it may be noted that the specific properties of these TiC-reinforced materials (based on 100% dense TiC particles, $\rho = 4900 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) are not better than any of the PM produced material, they approach these values and the cost saving verses PM produced material is expected to be very large.

Table 3. A comparison of the mechanical properties of commercial composites and materials produced in this work.

Composite	Modulus (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)	E / ρ
2014 T6-16% Al ₂ O ₃ (C, E) <i>Duralcan</i>	92	413	6	29.7
2080-20% SiC (PM) <i>Alcoa</i>	104	508	4	34.7
6XX1-15% SiC (PM) <i>Alcoa</i>	98	355	14	35.3
6061 T6-25% SiC (PM) <i>DWA</i>	98	409	4	34.7
A356 T6-20% SiC (C) <i>Duralcan</i>	97	352	0.4	34.6
CP Al-20% TiC (C) EXP	96	150	8	30.6
A356 T6-15% TiC (C) EXP	101	134	1.3	33.3
Al-4Cu-15% TiC (C) EXP	95	278	8	29.3
A356 T6-15% SiC (C) <i>Duralcan</i> EXP	88	174	1.3	31.7

DISCUSSION

COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURES

The grain refinement of Al with TiC particles present is expected due to the close face centred cubic crystal structure matching. The fluxing agents clean the TiC particle surfaces and hence a "fresh" interface is presented to the Al melt. Whilst not every particle acts as a grain nucleation site, it is clear that engulfment is favoured. In the Al-4Cu alloy system, where grain refinement is extensive, most particles are engulfed. In the A356 system, however, where grain refinement is less prominent, a larger proportion of the particles reside in the inter-dendritic regions. When the microstructures of the two A356 composites are compared, the proportion of inter-dendritic reinforcement is less for the TiC-reinforced composite than it is for the SiC-reinforced composite due to grain refining or "wetting" nature of TiC.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The modulus of TiC, is likely to be less than that of SiC (400 GPa) and Al₂O₃ (380 GPa) and we would not, therefore, have expected the strengthening effect to be as great. Large modulus increases, in conjunction with closer agreement with rule of mixtures predictions, even for upper limit values of the modulus, suggest that load transfer is more efficient in the TiC system most likely due to stronger interfacial bonding.

It is probable that the modulus of TiC in this case is close to the lower limit of 230 GPa since these particular reinforcements were made by carbothermic reduction of TiO₂ and are porous (evidence of which can be seen in the earlier micrographs). This fact helps to justify the modelling agreement and the reduced density of the particles will make the specific properties more attractive.

The low UTS and ductility values can be explained in terms of porosity in the castings and in some cases due to the presence of large inclusions. It has been observed that as more of these inclusions are removed, the mechanical properties rise significantly. More careful processing and an additional extrusion stage may help remove all the large inclusions, reduce porosity and improve the mechanical properties.

CONCLUSIONS

Al-TiC metal matrix composites have been produced with intra-dendritic distributions of the reinforcement.

The engulfment of the particles into the primary Al grains results in strong particle-matrix bonding which promotes efficient load transfer.

As a result of the improved load transfer, these composites have moduli which are much closer to those predicted by the rule of mixtures than in the case of SiC and Al₂O₃-reinforced composites.

The strong interfacial bonding delays the onset of particle-matrix de-cohesion resulting in large elongations or strains before failure.

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